

Hygrothermal evaluation of a construction component with textile waste: the case of AISLA-SUSTEX

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ABSTRACT

Our research team is developing a thermal insulation with a vapor barrier called AISLA-SUSTEX using pre-consumer textile waste as the main raw material. In this sense, to evaluate the hygrothermal conditions of the component under study, the value of thermal transmittance is taken from a previous work and in this work the risk of superficial and interstitial condensation is calculated according to the calculation methodology of the IRAM 11625 standard, through the C-RC calculator, taking as a case study a social housing in the Metropolitan Area of Tucumán, Argentina. The results show that this component improves the hygrothermal conditions of the interior space of the house and therefore, contributes to the healthiness of the users as well as to reduce construction pathologies.

KEYWORDS

Hygrothermal comfort, ecodesign, circular economy.

INTRODUCTION

The current civilization is in collapse due to the dominant paradigm of unlimited growth and governed by a linear economic system <extract-use-dispose>. This problem begins to become evident in the middle of the 20th century, becoming increasingly important (ONU, 2021). Currently, the textile industry and the construction sector face great challenges to reverse the environmental impact that is caused. On the one hand, if we focus on this industry, many critical points are evident within the life cycle of its products: use of virgin raw material for manufacturing, water contamination, little use of garments due to a lifestyle to the fashion. rapid incineration at the end of its useful life of large tons of disused clothing, etc. On the other hand, in the construction sector there is evidence of concern for representing 40% of non-renewable energy consumption and emissions to the environment worldwide (kuchen & Kosak,2020)

Based on the above, from a transition perspective towards circular models in both sectors, the use of textile waste for the manufacture of construction components is proposed. In this way, the concept of circular economy is applied, which raises the need to rethink the use of materials and energy in a restorative, regenerative, systemic and balanced way in all social classes (MacArthur Foundation, 2018). In other words, an attempt is made to decouple global economic development from the consumption of finite resources and establish a new paradigm which has society as its foundation and Nature as its roof (Raworth, 2018). Unlike the Linear Economy (LE), the Circular Economy (CE) aims to maintain the value of products, materials and resources in the economic circle for as long as possible (CAF, 2018). In this sense, it is inspired by nature and proposes a life cycle of products and/or services "from the cradle to the cradle", generating a closed flow of resources as opposed to planning "from the cradle to the grave" (Ecoplast, 2016), as observed in the current reality.

Faced with all the above, the use of textile waste and others for use in the construction sector is proposed. In the international commercial field, there are construction materials resolved with pre-consumer and post-consumer textile waste, such as the case of RMT-Nita® Cotton (2011), in Spain. Another example is that of the company Ecofibra (2016) in Chile or the group Bonded Logic Inc (2004) in the United States, its component is called UltraTouch. The latter is known for his help in the reconstruction of houses after Hurricane Katrina, within the "Cotton from Blue to Green" project. Universities in the United States collected 14,566 pieces of jeans to turn them into 40,000 m² of thermal insulation and implemented them in 12 homes. Another precedent is the FabBRICK project, by the French architect Clarisse Merlet, which recycles used clothes and turns them into bricks and/or thermal and acoustic insulating panels (Merlet, 2018). However, in the national and provincial context similar products are not detected. To this end, our research team is developing a thermal insulation with a vapor barrier. This technological alternative is called AISLA-SUSTEX (Saez et al., 2021) and its main raw material is pre-consumer textile waste, that is, remnants of "machine foot" from the making of different textile garments from local industries, among them others waste such as cardboard and plastic that improve their physical and technological properties.

Based on the above, this study tries to answer the following question: how is the hygrothermal behavior of AISLA-SUSTEX in residential buildings? The objective is to calculate the risk of superficial and interstitial condensation, according to the calculation methodology of the IRAM 11625 standard, through the C-RC calculator, in a social dwelling in the Metropolitan Area of Tucumán, Argentina, both in its current situation and in its improvement, proposal using the component under study. Noteworthy, data on the thermal evaluation of this component are taken from a previous work (Saez et al., 2021).

METHODOLY

In a first stage, it is proposed to characterize the AISLA-SUSTEX construction component developed by the work team where its physical and thermal properties are shown. In a second stage, the bioenvironmental zone of the analysis unit is defined, according to IRAM 11.603 standard, and the construction characteristics of the envelope are detailed, both in the base case and in the improved case. In addition, the results obtained in previous studies on thermal evaluation in both situations are included. In the third stage, the verifications on surface and interstitial condensation of the house in the current situation and the improvement proposal are exposed, according to the calculation methodology of the IRAM 11625 standard, through the C-RC calculator (Fernández et al., 2020).

RESULTS

Characterization of the AISLA-SUSTEX construction component

The thermal insulation designed by AISLA-SUSTEX contains pre-consumer textile waste as its main raw material, that is, remains of the foot of the machine from the manufacture of different textile garments. The choice of the raw material, in this first instance of the investigation, is based on the possibility of obtaining a clean material without the need to use water resources for its elaboration. These remnants of industries are generally mixtures of cotton, polyester and polyamides since the garments are not made up of a single textile raw material. ~~Si bien existen usos similares en el mercado mundial, se considera fundamental realizar una producción local del componente favoreciendo la cadena de valor de las pequeñas industrias y Pymes.~~ Although there are similar uses in the world market, it is considered essential to produce the component locally, favoring the value chain of small industries or small and medium-sized companies. As shown in Figure 1, after textile defibration, it is attached with white biodegradable glue (water, acetic acid or ethanoic acid and polysaccharide), then compacted and thus a plate is formed. To achieve greater rigidity and easy handling, a recycled corrugated cardboard is placed on its back and on that side of the element, a vapor barrier made with bilaminated high-density polypropylene plastic waste is added, always using biodegradable glue.

Figure 1: AISLA-SUSTEX. Source: Own elaboration.

It should be noted that the construction component is in the study phase, which is why the thermal conductivity values are taken for the textile waste layer of a similar material called RMT-Nita® Cotton. Likewise, the permeance and permeability data of the different layers of the prototype are taken from similar construction materials according to data from the IRAM 11601 standard. Table 1 shows the technical data of each of the layers that constitute the AISLA-SUSTEX construction component.

Table1: technical data AISLA-SUSTEX. Source: Own elaboration.

AISLA-SUSTEX	Dimensions (m)		Weight (Kg/m²)	Conductivity (W/m K)	Thermal Resistance (m².K/W)	Permeability (g/m.h.kPa)	Permeance (g/m².h.kPa)
Main raw materia:							
Remnants of textile industries. Cotton, polyester and polyamide blends	Length:	0,4	4,5	0,036	1,389	0,5	-
	Width:	0,4					
	Thickness:	0,05					
Complementary raw materials:							
Reused double wave corrugated cardboard	Length:	0,4	0,1	0,620	0,002	0,330	-
	Width:	0,4					
	Thickness:	0,001					
Reused bilaminated highdensity polypropylene plastic	length:	0,4	0,025	0,240	0,001	-	0,01
	width:	0,4					
	thickness:	0,0025					

Identification of the case study

The town where this type of social interest housing is located is defined as bio-environmental zone IIb, according to IRAM 11603 Standard. This is characterized by having a warm temperate climate, with thermal amplitudes greater than 14 °C, summer with average temperatures between 20 °C and 26 °C, with average maximums greater than 30 °C. Winter presents average temperature values between 8 °C and 12 °C, and minimum values that are rarely lower than 0 °C. In general, this area has relatively mild winters (IRAM, 2012). One of the most built housing typologies in the last 20 years by the Provincial Institute of Housing and Urban Development (IPVyDU) is taken as a case study. As shown in figure 2, it is a single-family home of 40 m² with two bedrooms and a bathroom. It materializes with hollow ceramic brick masonry 0.18m thick plastered on both sides, which is designated as Wall 1 (W1). The roof is light, called (R1), resolved with a trapezoidal sheet metal roof, 0.050m thick glass wool thermal insulation, and a 0.009m thick plasterboard suspended ceiling. Aluminum carpentry with simple glass, without thermal bridge breaker and without solar protection, see figure 3.

Figure 2: Planimetry base case social housing 40 m². Source: Own elaboration based on the IPVyDU.

Referencias:

1. Sheet iron
2. Glass wool
3. Steel beam
4. Steel beam
5. Reinforced concrete
6. Ventilated air chamber
7. Ceiling
8. Plaster
9. Ceramic Brick
10. Plaster

Figure 3: base case envelope. Source: Own elaboration.

Table 2 shows the values of the coefficient of thermal transmittance U ($W/m^2 K$) for the winter situation and the values of thermal resistance of the construction elements of the envelope -wall and roof-. Likewise, they are compared with the maximum admissible K_{MAX} ADM values according to IRAM 11,900 standard and the level of hygrothermal comfort with which they verify is determined. Note that the W1 and R1 support level C -minimum- and in the case of R1 also level B -medium- stipulated by the standard.

Table 2: Base case thermal values .Source: Own elaboration.

Base Case		Thermal transmittance coefficient U ($W/m^2 K$)			Resistance ($m^2.K/W$)
Wall		Winter			0,69
		1,43			
Roof		Winter			0,66
		0,63			
Verification IRAM 11900	Level A	Level A-B	Level B	Level C	
	0,38	0,69	1	1,85	
Wall 1	-	-	-	✓	
Verification IRAM 11900	Level A	Level A-B	Level B	Level C	
	0,32	0,58	0,83	1	
Roof 2	-	-	✓	✓	

In the energy rehabilitation of the envelope, an improvement of the type Exterior Thermal Insulation System with dry technology using the thermal insulation with vapor barrier AISLA-SUSTEX,

hereinafter referred to as (W2), is proposed for the wall. It should be noted that the AISLA-SUSTEX is placed with its vapor barrier facing the exterior plaster. Likewise, in the ceiling, designated as (TL2)(R2), this insulation is proposed to be incorporated into the interior of the attic, placing the vapor barrier on the suspended ceiling, see figure 4.

Figure 4: Improved AISLA-SUSTEX proposal. Source: Own elaboration.

Table 3 shows the transmittance and thermal resistance values for the winter situation of W2 and R2. Also, these results are compared with the maximum admissible KMAX ADM values according to IRAM 11,900 standard and it is determined in the levels of hygrothermal comfort with which they verify. It is noted that both the W2 and R2 supports even up to level A/B -intermediate-.

Table 3: Base case construction elements. Source: Own elaboration.

Improved Case with AISLA-SUSTEX		Thermal transmittance coefficient (W/m ² K)			Resistance (m ² .K/W)
Wall 2		Situation Winter			2,115
		0,46			
Roof 2		Situation Winter			0,66
		0,32			
Verification IRAM 11900	Level A	Level A-B	Level B	Level C	
	0,38	0,69	1	1,85	
Wall 2	-	✓	✓	✓	
Verification IRAM 11900	Level A	Level A-B	Level B	Level C	
	0,32	0,58	0,83	1	
Roof 2	-	✓	✓	✓	

Verification risk of condensation:

The risk of surface and interstitial water vapor condensation is calculated according to IRAM 11,625 and 11,630 standards through the C-RC calculator (Fernandez et al., 2020) for both the vertical and horizontal enclosures of the envelope. The calculation of the central panels is carried out considering a distance of 0.5 m with respect to the ends and of the sectors of edges and corners as they are the most unfavorable to the risks of condensation. The minimum design outdoor temperature of the place is adopted according to Table A.1 (IRAM 11.603) being for San Miguel de Tucumán -0.2 °C, and then the design indoor temperature is set using Table 2 (IRAM 11.625) according to the destination of the premises or the function of the building, and it is considered that it is 18°C for dwellings. The exterior relative humidity was taken at 90% and the design interior relative humidity (HRI) will be 69%. Regarding the values adopted for the internal and external surface resistance, those stipulated by the IRAM 11630 standard are taken. In this way, it is considered for central panels 0.17 m².K/W and in edges and corners it is taken 0, 34 m².K/W. Likewise, the external surface resistance in both cases is 0.04 m².K/W according to the specifications of the standard according to the horizontal direction of heat flow for walls in winter. The thicknesses and thermal properties of the different layers of the components are taken from the IRAM 11.601 standard, see table 4.

Table 4: Climatic characteristics of the site. Source: Own elaboration.

Climatic characteristics of the site		
Location:		San Miguel de Tucumán
Winter design indoor temperature:	°C	18
Winter design outside Temperature	°C	-0.2
Indoor Design Relative Humidity:	%	69
Outside Design Relative Humidity:	%	90

Figure 5 shows the results obtained for W1 and W2. The different layers of the construction components are observed from the inside to the outside of the building and the variation of the real and dew temperature in each layer. It is determined that in M1, there is no risk of surface condensation, in its central panels, however, in the edges and corners, it does verify risks. As for the risks of interstitial condensation, it admits risk both in the central panels and in the edges and corners in the outer plaster layer. According to what is observed in the graph, the abrupt decrease in real temperature is generated in the hollow brick component due to its low thermal resistance. In the case of W2, it is observed that there is no risk of surface condensation in central panels and edges and corners. In addition, the risk of interstitial condensation is avoided since the AISLA-SUSTEX placed on the outside of the construction element adds thermal resistance and resistance to the diffusion of water vapour. In this way, it is possible to maintain similar real temperature values between each layer of the construction element and higher than the dew temperature. It should be clarified that for the calculations carried out, the component under study is considered for the physical and thermal properties of each sub-layer or each raw material -textile, cardboard and plastic- where each of these provide different values of conductivity, density and permeability or permeance.

Figure 5: Verification of risk of condensation in W1 y W2. Source: Own elaboration.

In figure 6, it is determined that TL1 does not present a risk of superficial condensation both in its central panels and in its edges and corners. However, in both areas there is a risk of interstitial condensation in the galvanized sheet metal layer. In TL2, where the incorporation of greater thermal insulation and vapor barrier with AISLA-SUSTEX is proposed, it is observed that there is no risk of superficial or interstitial condensation in both central sections and areas of edges and corners.

Figure 6: Verification of risk of condensation in TL1 y TL2. Source: Own elaboration.

DISCUSSION

For a better assessment of the prototype under study, the risk of surface and interstitial condensation of a third option is also verified, where AISLA-SUSTEX is replaced with polystyrene (EPS) with a thickness of 0.05m. In this option, a SATE wall is proposed with dry technology with a thermal insulation of Expanded Polystyrene of 0.05m, called from here on (W3), in the light ceiling EPS of 0.050m of thickness is also added and designates as (R3). Figure 7 shows the values of the verification of the risk of superficial and interstitial condensation of W2 and W3 in their most unfavorable situation, that is, areas of edges and corners. It is observed that both W2 and W3 do not present risks of superficial and interstitial condensation, however, the real temperatures are more distant with respect to the dew temperature in the case of W2 with AISLA-SUSTEX, which shows a better behavior of this in comparison to the use of EPS.

Figure 7: Verification of risk of condensation in W2 y W3. Source: Own elaboration.

In the case of the results obtained for the ceilings, it can be seen in figure 8 that the case of R2 with AISLA-SUSTEX does not present risks of superficial and interstitial condensation. On the other hand, in R3 it does not condense in the surface layer but in the layer of glass wool and galvanized sheet.

Figure 8: Verification of risk of condensation in R2 y R3. Source: Own elaboration.

As Fernandez and Garzón (2020) say, the risk of interstitial condensation is due to the conductivity and permeability values of the materials, while the superficial one is an exclusive consequence of the low thermal insulation. In the previous results, it is evident that the incorporation of a multilayer heterogeneous material improves the thermal resistance and the passage of water vapor of the construction element. Likewise, the importance of locating the material that works as a vapor barrier prior to the planned thermal insulation is highlighted.

CONCLUSION

Through this research, it is concluded that the AISLA-SUSTEX construction component has optimal hygrothermal properties, that is, it improves the resistance of the envelope and prevents risks of surface and interstitial condensation, avoiding some construction pathologies and favoring the healthiness of the environment. Likewise, the type of construction system that is proposed for use in construction allows it to be used both for existing projects and for new construction. In addition, it is noted that for each m² of manufacturing of this material, 4.5 kg of shredded textile, 0.1 kg of corrugated cardboard and 0.025 kg of polypropylene are reused, which means that to cover the envelope of a housing prototype, uses 517.5 kg of textile, 11.5 kg of corrugated cardboard and 2.87 kg of bilaminated plastic. Therefore, it is important to highlight that from the construction sector in collaboration with other industries there are many possibilities to make sustainable technological contributions. In this way, favor the reduction of material and energy consumption and generate a transition to circular models of production of materials, as well as of the building throughout its life cycle. Through this type of construction materials resolved with waste, the architectural design, materials and construction techniques can be totally or partially replaced without losing hygrothermal comfort. In other words, they are a suitable and superior solution for the execution of thermal construction components, being a sustainable alternative with triple impact: social, economic and environmental. On the one hand, the useful life of materials that, considered waste, contaminate soils, seas and air is extended, and on the other, they are raw materials of low economic cost and can directly or indirectly benefit many sectors of society.

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CONFLICT OF INTEREST

The authors declare that they have no conflicts of interest associated with the work presented in this paper.

DATA AVAILABILITY

1. Data on which this paper is based is available from the authors upon reasonable request.